

The order of stability constants of mixed ligand chelates with the change in secondary ligands is $HQ > 1-HNA > 3-HNA > ARS$. This can be explained on the basis of size of these ligands. The bulkier ligand attachment to primary complex will be steriospecifically hindered and will destabilise the complex. The order of stability constants of mixed ligand chelates with respect to primary ligands is

$$K_{MAL}^{NTA} > K_{MAL}^{HEDTA} > K_{MAL}^{EDTA} > K_{MAL}^{CDTA}$$

The values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ show that the stability of these mixed ligand chelates decreases with the increase in temperature. All the secondary ligands act as bidentate and effective coordination number for samarium(III) in these species is six, seven and eight in the case of NTA, HEDTA, EDTA = CDTA, respectively. From the results it can be suggested that the coordination number of samarium can be expanded more than six.

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Polarographic Behaviour of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-Nitroacetanilides in Aqueous Mixtures of Organic Solvents *vis-a-vis* Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

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A survey of literature reveals that polarographic behaviour of nitroacetanilides in aqueous mixtures of inert organic solvents *vis-a-vis* kinetics of the electrode reaction has not been studied so far. Hence, the title study has been undertaken in aqueous mixtures of methanol, ethanol, propanol, butanol and dimethylformamide.

Experimental

ortho-, *meta*- and *para*-Nitroacetanilides (B.D.H.) were recrystallised from ethanol before use. The other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The concentration of each depolariser was maintained at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. Desired concentrations of various constituents of BR buffer of pH 6.1 were added to the solution to be polarographed. $NaNO_3$ (0.1 M) was used as a supporting electrolyte. A Toshniwal PL 02 manual polarograph in conjunction with a Toshniwal PL 50 polyflex galvanometer was used. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (S. C. E.). The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction of the nitroacetanilides was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon¹. It gave the value of n equal to 4 for each depolariser at pH 6.1. Having known the value of n , Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of D , the diffusion coefficient of nitroacetanilides in the presence of aqueous mixtures of organic solvents. The potential-dependent rate constant $k_{f,h}$ was calculated by Koutecky's method^{2,3}. The kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ were calculated⁴ from the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{d.s.}$. Throughout the measurements current at the end of the drop (*i.e.* the maximum current) was recorded for the reasons given by Meites^{5,6}. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: $m=2.71 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t=3.4 \text{ s}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.38 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ (in 0.1 M $NaNO_3$, open circuit); $h_{oorr} = 32.3 \text{ cm}$.

Results and Discussion

ortho-, *meta*- and *para*-Nitroacetanilides yield a single well-defined wave (pH 6.1) in the presence of increasing percentage of different organic solvents. The waves become drawn out at higher percentages of propanol and DMF. The reduction of each depolariser is diffusion-controlled as evidenced by the fact that the plots of i_d vs $h_{oorr}^{1/2}$ are linear and pass through the origin. Various criteria for ascertaining the irreversibility of the polarographic reduction of the nitroacetanilides in the presence of increasing percentages of organic solvents were applied. The slope values (Table 1) of log plots in each case are much larger than the theoretical values expected for a 4-electron reversible reduction process. From this it follows that the polarographic reduction of the nitroacetanilides is irreversible^{5,6}. Further, the theory of irreversible waves^{6,7} predicts that the current is independent of the pressure head of mercury at the foot of the wave and becomes diffusion-controlled at the top, varying linearly with $h_{oorr}^{1/2}$. This dependence of the current on h_{oorr} at different stages of the wave was also studied. It was found that the current was independent of h_{oorr} at the foot of the wave whereas it was proportional to $h_{oorr}^{1/2}$ at the plateau of the wave.

NOTES

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR ELECTRODE REACTIONS OF NITROACETANILIDES IN PRESENCE OF AQUEOUS ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Organic solvent % (v/v)	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ (S.C.E.) V	Slope mV	D $\times 10^6 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\alpha n a$	k_f, h cm s^{-1}	k_f^0, h cm s^{-1}
<i>o</i> -Nitroacetanilide							
Methanol							
10	17.11	0.310	70	6.48	0.82	70.7	1.32×10^{-4}
20	16.39	0.320	85	5.94	0.70	39.8	1.40×10^{-4}
30	14.97	0.330	92	4.96	0.63	25.1	1.28×10^{-4}
40	14.26	0.345	98	4.50	0.59	15.8	9.37×10^{-5}
Ethanol							
10	16.39	0.320	60	5.94	0.97	56.2	6.00×10^{-5}
20	14.26	0.330	65	4.50	0.89	31.6	6.69×10^{-5}
30	13.54	0.355	74	4.05	0.78	12.5	5.10×10^{-5}
49	12.12	0.360	83	3.25	0.70	10.0	3.38×10^{-5}
Propanol							
10	14.26	0.360	80	4.50	0.73	10.0	3.48×10^{-5}
20	12.83	0.420	85	3.64	0.68	1.9	7.98×10^{-6}
30	12.12	0.445	93	3.25	0.62	1.5	8.27×10^{-6}
49	Wave drawn out						
DMF							
10	15.68	0.380	65	5.44	0.89	5.6	9.08×10^{-6}
20	14.97	0.460	85	4.96	0.68	1.0	6.28×10^{-6}
30	Wave drawn out						
<i>m</i> -Nitroacetanilide							
Methanol							
10	16.39	0.370	70	5.94	0.83	31.6	1.88×10^{-5}
20	15.68	0.380	75	5.44	0.77	19.9	1.75×10^{-5}
30	14.26	0.390	84	4.50	0.69	11.2	1.86×10^{-5}
40	12.83	0.415	93	3.64	0.62	6.3	1.38×10^{-5}
Ethanol							
10	16.39	0.360	65	5.94	0.89	50.1	1.89×10^{-5}
20	12.83	0.390	70	3.64	0.83	12.5	7.44×10^{-6}
30	11.40	0.415	80	2.87	0.72	5.0	8.17×10^{-6}
40	10.69	0.420	92	2.52	0.66	3.5	8.69×10^{-6}
Propanol							
10	12.83	0.410	75	3.64	0.77	7.0	5.79×10^{-6}
20	11.40	0.500	90	2.87	0.64	1.7	6.28×10^{-6}
30	Wave drawn out						
DMF							
10	15.68	0.390	70	5.44	0.83	15.8	9.07×10^{-6}
20	13.54	0.410	80	4.05	0.72	7.0	8.45×10^{-6}
30	12.83	0.510	95	3.64	0.61	1.1	8.58×10^{-6}
40	Wave drawn out						
<i>p</i> -Nitroacetanilide							
Methanol							
10	21.39	0.440	90	10.12	0.64	70.7	1.09×10^{-5}
20	19.25	0.480	100	8.20	0.59	22.3	6.28×10^{-6}
30	16.39	0.495	110	5.94	0.55	12.5	6.18×10^{-6}
40	13.54	0.515	122	4.05	0.53	3.1	4.66×10^{-6}
Ethanol							
10	20.67	0.450	80	9.54	0.72	63.0	4.28×10^{-6}
20	19.96	0.490	95	8.81	0.61	19.9	3.88×10^{-6}
30	17.82	0.515	105	7.02	0.58	10.0	4.28×10^{-6}
40	16.39	0.340	115	5.94	0.53	5.0	3.06×10^{-6}
Propanol							
10	29.96	0.510	95	8.81	0.61	12.5	2.37×10^{-6}
20	19.25	0.600	110	8.20	0.53	1.7	8.35×10^{-7}
30	Wave drawn out						
DMF							
10	21.39	0.480	105	10.12	0.64	25.1	9.19×10^{-6}
20	19.96	0.580	110	8.81	0.60	10.0	1.39×10^{-6}
30	16.39	0.599	118	5.94	0.58	5.6	2.28×10^{-6}
40	13.54	0.602	122	4.05	0.54	5.0	4.32×10^{-6}

The nitroacetanilides are reduced at pH 6.1 in a single step which corresponds to a 4-electron reduction process. Thus, the reduction of the nitroacetanilides at this pH is analogous to the reduction of nitrobenzene. The 4-electron reduction process of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-nitroacetanilides represents their reduction to the corresponding phenylhydroxylamine derivatives. Since the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{a.o.}$ in the presence of different organic solvents are linear, there is only one rate-determining step^{8,9} involved in the electroreduction of each depolariser. The influence of increasing amounts of organic solvents on the kinetics of the irreversible electrode reactions of the nitroacetanilides is discussed below in terms of the values of the kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$.

From Table 1 it is evident that the product αn_a decreases with increasing amounts of all the organic solvents. The values of αn_a lie in the range 0.53-0.97 in the presence of different organic solvents. An attempt to estimate n_a , the number of electrons involved in the rate-determining step, apparently leads to a conclusion^{8,10} that n_a is equal to 2 because for totally irreversible systems as the present ones are, α should be less than¹¹ 0.5. However, only a single electron can be transferred at a time during the course of an electrode reaction^{8,9}, a value of n_a exceeding 1 should merely mean that the successive steps are too nearly simultaneous to be distinguished on the time scale implicit in the polarographic measurements. Thus, whether n_a is 1 or 2, the change in αn_a values can only be due to a change in α . It is thus concluded that it is α which is decreasing, thus implies that the transfer of electron(s) is made increasingly difficult. In other words, the electrode reactions of the nitroacetanilides are rendered increasingly more irreversible with increasing amounts of organic solvents.

A perusal of Table 1 reveals that there is no regularity in the variation of $k_{f,h}^0$ values with increasing amounts of organic solvents. It has also been hinted^{5a} at the limitation of $k_{f,h}^0$ in interpreting the results. However, the influence of increasing amounts of organic solvents on the electrode reactions of the nitroacetanilides can be studied in terms of the value of the potential-dependent rate constant ($k_{f,h}$) at a suitable potential which should be such as to lie between the potentials corresponding to the foot and the plateau of the polarographic wave. At such a potential both the rate of the electron-transfer and the diffusion determine the magnitude of the current. In the present study this potential has been taken as -0.36, -0.40 and -0.5 V (vs S.C.E.) for *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-nitroacetanilides, respectively. A perusal of Table 1 shows that $k_{f,h}$ decreases with increasing amounts of organic solvents. From this it follows that the electrode reactions of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-nitroacetanilides are rendered more

irreversible with increasing amounts of the organic solvents. These conclusions are in harmony with those arrived at on the basis of the variation in αn_a values.

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Extraction and Recovery of some Carboxylic Acids by Flexible Polyurethane Foam from Water

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THE discovery of polyurethane foams to retain a number of compounds including polychlorinated biphenyls, organochlorine pesticides, phthalate esters etc. from water¹, developed a growing interest in using this technique to concentrate other compounds as well. Therefore, an attempt has been made to study the column chromatographic behaviour of some carboxylic acids on flexible polyurethane foam plugs in water.

Polyurethane foam plugs of different diameters (d) were cut from 45 mm thick flexible polyurethane foam sheet (J. J. Products, India). Aqueous or ethanolic solutions of carboxylic acids (Sigma) and aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (Ranbaxy) were prepared. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

To determine the amounts of the carboxylic acids obtained from water, the foam plugs (19 mm d. \times 90 mm) were wetted with distilled water for 15 min and placed in a glass column (17 mm i.d.). 0.001 N of the acid solutions (100 ml) were passed through the column at $28 \pm 2^\circ$ and at boiling